

EDEN ISS

Lighting System Design Document

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Executive summary

The following document describes the design and implementation of the Heliospectra lights in the EDEN ISS project. An overview is given of the specifications of the different lights, the layout of the lighting units within the Mobile Test Facility (MTF) and the operations related to the lighting system. Furthermore, some lessons learned during the design process are presented.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
CPU	Central processing unit	PAR	Photosynthetically active radiation
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	PSU	Power supply unit
ISPR	International Standard Payload Rack	UI	User interface
MTF	Mobile Test Facility		

1 Top-level design overview

Both the ISPR and FEG illumination systems are based on a new water-cooled fixture. The working name for the fixture is WX and it is based on the LX/RX/E product platform.

Key features of the WX:

- Compact – 210 x 372 x 86 mm.
- Control – The fixture shares the same means of IP based control via Ethernet as the standard LX product.
- Thermal – Each lamp is equipped with a cold plate. At a flow of 1 l/min the LED plate temperature is approx. 4 degrees higher than the coolant inlet temperature.
- Power – The WX is designed with two alternate power supplies, 120W and 240W.
- Spectral quality - The light spectrum will be produced by 450, 660 and 735 nm LEDs along with a broadband white 5700K LED. The resulting spectrum will have the following composition:
 - 15% blue (400-500 nm)
 - 10% green (500-600 nm)
 - 75% red (600-700 nm)
 - 2% far-red (700-750 nm)

The OSRAM LED part numbers at the time of writing are:

- 450nm LD CQDP-2U3U-W5-1
- 660nm LH CPDP-3T4T-1
- 735nm GF CSHPM1.24-3S4S-1
- 5700K LCW CRDP.PC-LRLT-5F7G-1-R18
- Dimming - Each wavelength is independently dimmable.
- IP rating – The WX is designed to comply with IP65 or better ratings.
- Design – The housing is made of aluminum with tracks compatible with Item system fasteners such as the Item System Angle Bracket V 5 20 Zn (part no: 0.0.612.79).
- Intra-canopy light – In addition to the WX, full illumination lighting will be used to provide more light when plants in chamber R3 (tallest rack) are small.

Figure 1-1: Rendered illustration of the Heliospectra WX water cooled LED fixture.

The light bars selected for use in chamber R3 are of the prototype model: LightBar V71G. Its key features are:

- Size - 123.5 x 5.6 x 6.2 cm

- Spectral quality – The light spectrum will be produced by 450 and 660 nm LEDs along with a broadband white 5700K LED.
- Photon flux - 113 $\mu\text{mol/s}$
- Power – Either a 75W driver, or a 150W driver (for two bars)
- IP rating – The V71G is designed to meet IP66 rating (still under testing progress)
- Dimming – Optional dimming between 5 – 100% is possible with a 0-10V signal

Figure 1-2: Illustration of the Heliospectra LightBar

2 Detailed design

2.1 Block Diagram

Figure 2-1: Block Diagram.

2.1.1 Fixture Design

The WX fixture is based on the current LX design. From the LX the LED plate platform, CPU control card, optics and connectors have been reused. The new components in the WX are found in the cooling system and housing.

The WX is a self-contained unit in that the power supply and control board are located within the housing.

An outer aluminum extrusion encloses the internal layers. The two end pieces with gaskets and a gasket around the front glass provide ingress protection.

From a functional perspective the fixture has the composition shown in Figure 2-2.

Figure 2-2: WX fixture block diagram.

At the system border Ethernet, 230 VAC and coolant are provided. The interactions between the functional blocks are as follows:

- Upon start up the CPU card reads the LED configuration (C) from the LED plate via I2C. This allows the same CPU card firmware to operate different LED configurations.
- HTTP light commands via Ethernet are translated to current settings (I x 4) for the LED strings on the LED plate.
- Temperature (T) data can be read from the LED plate upon request over HTTP.
- The PSU converts 230 VAC to 48 VDC for both the LED plate and CPU card.
- Cooling is provided to both the LED plate and the PSU via the liquid cold plate.

The WX is compatible with different power supplies depending on the application. For the EDEN ISS project the Mean Well 120W constant voltage power supply (HLG-120H series) and the Mean Well 240W constant voltage power supply (HLG-240H series) will be implemented.

2.2 System sizing/analyses

Prior to the full shipment of WX lights, plant cultivation tests and plant analyzes (WP4 lead byWUR) needed to be conducted therefore Heliospectra provided LX60 commercial type (HLB607) fixtures (with active air cooling) with special EDEN type LED plates. A total of 34 such fixtures were produced; 24 for plant performance test in WUR, 10 for plant safety and integration tests in DLR, LIT and TAS.

In total 44 WX will be used by the EDEN ISS project (42 WX within the FEG and 2 WX within the ISPR). Within the FEG, one WX will be used over each tray. One WX will be used over each tray in the short and tall compartments (see block diagram and Figure 2-3). Each WX over the short trays will run at 120W. Over the tall trays the WX will run at 240W. In addition to the overhead WX lighting, the full height vine shelf (rack R3) will provide full illumination lighting via the use of static light bars (1 to 2).

Figure 2-3: FEG rack and tray configuration.

2.2.1 Light plan

The lights in the FEG facility (with plants) were measured and adjusted to achieve light intensity and quality similar to the specifications described in the cultivation recipes.

A portable JAZ spectrometer was used to determine the light spectra. A hand-held portable Li-cor PAR meter was also used. Lights were measured at the middle of 3 shelves, representing the short, medium and tall crops:

- L2_1L (Short crops) at 16 and 25 cm above the lid of a growth container
- L1_2R (Medium crops) at 25 and 60 cm above the lid of a growth container

- R3_R (Tall crops) measured between two lights at 30, 50, 60, 120 cm above the lid of a growth container and additionally between 15 and 20 cm from the lamp (only with PAR meter).

The light spectrum output of the lamps was set to approximately 17:12:71 (Blue - 400-500nm: Green -500-600nm: Red - 600-700nm)

Because the lamps were designed to have much higher percentage of Red (according to the first specification) it proved difficult or impossible with the lowest lamps' settings.

Crops were divided into 7 light regime groups according to expected height and light requirements. The intermediate light settings were estimated. Settings for light period before "sunset" and after "sunrise" can be calculated by dividing the "day" settings by 2.

Table 2-1: Crops expected height, light requirements and light regime group.

Crop ^a	Cultivar ^a	Shelf/crop height ^a	Light intensity recommended ^b	Regime group
Seedlings		L	200	0
Lettuce	'Experise' 'Othile' 'Outredgeous'	L/ 25	300	B
Rocket		L/ 20	300	B
Red mustard		L /25	300	B
Swiss chard		30	300	B
Spinach	all	L/10-15	300	A
Radish	all	L 15-20	600	C
Parsley		L 15-25	300	B
Tomato	dwarf	M/ 40	300	E
Tomato	'Candy Tom'	M	300	E
Cucumber	all	T	300	F
Lettuce	'Pulsar'	L 10	300	A
Coriander		L 30	300	B
Basil		L 30	300	B
Pepper	middle height	M 90	300	E
Pepper	high	T	300	F
Chives		L/ 25-35	600	D

^a According table 3 and 4 in Cultivation recipe

^b $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ table 5 in Cultivation recipe

Table 2-2: Suggested light settings for specific groups

Light regime group	Shelf	Description	Plant growth phase	Day settings for lamps				% of different colour waveband ^a			PAR ^b
				B 450	R 660	FR 735	W 5700K	B	G	R	
O	Low	seedlings	-	58	23	64	28				220
A	Low	Short/300	≤15cm	90	36	100	44	17.2	12.5	70.3	330
B	Low	Tall/300	≤15cm	90	36	100	44	17.2	12.5	70.3	330
			15-20	68	27	100	33				
			more	46	18	100	22	17.5	12.7	69.9	330
C	Low	Short/600	≤15cm	100	72	100	90	13.5	13.3	73.3	600
D	Low	Taller/600	≤15cm	100	72	100	90	13.5	13.3	73.3	600
			15-20	95	54	100	67				
			20-30	90	36	100	44	17.5	12.5	70	660
			>30	68	27	60	33				
E	Mid.	300	>15cm	90	36	100	44	16.7	11.7	71.6	450 at 25cm
			c.25	60	17	100	20	17	12.2	70.7	305
			>60	18	15	60	15	11	12	77	652
F	Tall	300	TBD*								

*possibly 100, 36, 100, 44, and keep plant at least 18 cm from the lamp.

^a Blue 400-500nm; Green 500-600nm Red 600-700nm

^b μmol m⁻²s⁻¹ measured at 16 cm , 25 cm or 60 cm, accordingly.

Figure 2-4: Example light spectrum, lamp L2_1L at 25 cm from the tray lid. PAR intensity of $330 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$

2.2.2 Thermal management

The thermal characteristics of the lamp for high power have been simulated below. A flow rate of 1 l/min with an input temperature of 18°C has been assumed. In the simulations two lamps have been connected in series as this is the installation principle within the FEG.

The conditions in the simulation are such that each cold plate has a heat load of 160W which corresponds to 350 W lamp power. The coolant characteristics at the inlet are assumed to be 18°C water with 20% glycol. The coolant temperature at the outlet of the second lamp is 22.8°C. The warmest point on the second lamp is just below 25°C.

Cooling liquid: 1 l/min, 18°C -> 22.8°C, 20% glycol
Effect: 2 x 160 W evenly distributed over 240 x 145 mm

Figure 2-5: Thermal simulation steady state heat load of the WX.

Bench top tests performed on early prototype fixture confirm the simulation results (Figure 2-5).

Figure 2-6: Bench top thermal testing (Picture is from an early prototype. The design in the picture does not correspond to the final design. The picture is merely illustrative of the bench top testing procedure).

Figure 2-7: Radiant power vs temperature Oslon SSL 150 Datasheet, v1.2, 2015-01-08.

The power per lamp will be lower in the FEG than the simulated case. Also LED output efficiency is stable between 20 and 40 °C (as illustrated in Figure 2-6). Therefore there should be an opportunity to do one of the following things:

- Increase the coolant temperature to reduce the power consumption of the thermal system.
- Connect more lamps in series to simplify coolant connections to the main coolant supply.
- Reduce the flow rate and potentially the size of the coolant pump.

2.2.3 Pressure characteristics

The pressure characteristics of the WX can be found in the diagram below. The curve is based on simulations for the cold plate design documentation. Note that this is without water fittings. At 1 l/min a pressure drop of 0.03 bar is expected. With water fittings the pressure drop will be slightly higher.

Figure 2-8: Pressure drop.

2.2.4 Power

The electrical power needed per tray is estimated as approx. 120 W for the 300 μmol/m²/s trays and 240 W per tray for the 600 μmol/m²/s trays. The estimates assume the system losses per tray in the 600 μmol/m²/s case shown in Figure 2-8.

Figure 2-9: Estimated electrical power losses for the 600 μmol/m²/s intensity case on a per tray basis.

The total electrical power for illumination is 9450W including a 25% margin.

Table 2-3: Total electrical power for illumination.

Description	Intensity on canopy (μmol/m ² /s)	Power per fixture (W)	Fixture quantity	Total power (W)
FEG				
Tall crops	600	240	18	4320
Short crops	300	120	18	2160
Germination	150	120	6	720
ISPR				
Tall crops	600	240	1	240
Small crops	300	120	1	120
			Total	7560
			Margin 25%	1890
			Total incl. margin	9450

2.3 Options and trades

The main trade off has been between using a compact box design and using light bars. The conclusion was to use a box design. The main driving factor has been that many of the internal components can be reused from the LX product family. This reduces risk in the project. Also a water cooled LX currently has more commercial viability.

In the R3 rack the WX top light will be complemented by a static light bar. This will either be a Heliospectra convection cooled light bar or a light bar of another brand. The Heliospectra convection cooled optimized bar is currently under development and will be ready Q2 2016.

The following two sections convey the trade-offs between a light bar and box based design identified during the CE study from Q3 2015.

2.3.1 Light bar

A light bar design would use multiple water cooled light bars that run the length of a shelf covering two trays. For short plants in lower intensity trays, two light bars would be used. For the higher intensity trays and taller plants, three light bars would be used.

The benefits of the light bar design:

- The light bars run almost the full length of the shelf and can be angled inward the coverage across the shelf can be good.
- A narrow bodied light bar allows a simple design of a water cooled fixture by creating a single water pathway in the fixture extrusion.

The light bar is a line source. To provide uniform coverage across a shelf several sources must be used. This has the following drawbacks:

- More water fittings are needed compared with the LED plate design.
- A separate control board box is needed.
- Creating a uniform spectrum becomes more difficult with a linear source as the LEDs with the highest efficiency available in the wavelengths needed for horticulture are high power LEDs (1-3 W). They can be placed in a line and driven harder to be more cost efficient but less uniform or they can be placed in multiple lines and driven less hard improving uniformity but also increasing cost.
- A separate design needs to be developed for the ISPR as the light bars will not fit the form factor of the ISPR.
- The current Heliospectra water cooled bar does not have separate wavelength control. Introducing this adds risk to the project.

2.3.2 LED plate

A box/LED plate design would centre a fixture over each tray. As the lights are dimmable the intensity across a shelf is controlled by the intensity setting and similar configurations can be used regardless if the tray is short/low or tall/high.

The benefits of the LED plate design:

- The same design that is used in the current dimmable Heliospectra products can be used in the EDEN ISS project. There is synergy with commercial customers seeking a controllable water cooled system.
- A common mechanical interface can be used across all shelves and in the ISPR.
- Slightly fewer water fittings will be needed than in the light bar case.
- The spectrum will be more uniform as the relative distance between LEDs of different wavelengths will be smaller than in the linear case.

The drawbacks of the LED plate design:

- As the LED plate is smaller than the tray, care needs to be taken so that light is distributed evenly across the tray and not too much light is lost to the walk way.

- Distributing water through the LED plate may be a bit more complicated than the case with the light bar.
- The amount of Ethernet cables is higher compared to the bar version, because each LED plate needs a separate cable while in the bar configuration one cable was sufficient per level (2-3 light bars).

2.4 Subsystem key values

Table 2-4 provides an overview of the key mass and power values of the lighting subsystem.

Table 2-4: Key values of the Lighting subsystem.

	Mass	Peak power	Power day - nominal mode	Power night - nominal mode
Mobile Test Facility	310 kg	10000W	9450 W	0 W
Neumayer Station III	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Spares, consumables, tools	44,7kg	N/A	N/A	N/A
TOTAL	354,7 kg	10000 W	9450 W	0 W

Note the difference between the nominal and peak power. The reason for this difference is due to the option to be able to go beyond the 300 µmol/m2/s level for some of the small plant compartments in the FEG. At the time of writing the quantity of high power fixtures in the small crop compartments has not been decided.

Note that the actual power consumption of the lighting system is dependent on the actual settings which will be implemented during the operations phase. The power consumption will be measured with an energy measurement system built into the main power distribution box.

3 Operations

3.1 Nominal operations

3.1.1 Setup

Each of the lights has an internal HTTP end point (a webserver). The web server publishes both a UI (webpage) but also allows machine-to-machine control. The Argus system will be the main UI for the control system and it will use the HTTP interface of the lamps.

3.1.1.1 IP addresses

Initially each lamp is given a static IP address. The reason for a static address is to reduce the need for a separate router. The physical position of each lamp can also be associated with the IP address. Regardless of the addressing scheme there are standard tools that can be used to assign IP addresses during commissioning.

The IP addresses for the lights need to be stored in the Argus system.

3.1.1.2 Intensity settings

A close approximation of the settings can be done before installation and commissioning of the system. However, the light settings should be measured and fine-tuned during installation. When the lamps have been mounted in the shelves the intensity settings that will be used in operation are calibrated.

Using a quantum meter (e.g. Licor 190R) the light settings that provide 300 / 600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ can be determined and recorded.

3.1.2 Operation

During operation the Argus system contains the schedule and settings for the shelves. When a light setting is to be adjusted the Argus system sends an HTTP request per lamp. The format of the request is

```
http://<address>/intensity.cgi?int=<450nm>:<660nm>:<735nm>:<5700K>
```

The intensity values are between 0 and 1000. All values must be sent even if only a single LED group is being changed.

```
http://10.1.4.3/intensity.cgi?int=0:0:0:0          Turn all LEDs off
```

```
http://10.1.4.3/intensity.cgi?int=500:500:500:0    Blue, red and white at 50%
```

The temperature of each lamp can be requested by querying for the status.xml for each lamp. The temperature can be found in the <i> field of the response. It may also be of interest to read back the intensities settings in the lamp. They can be found in the <j> field. An excerpt of a status.xml file can be found below. Complete documentation of the format is available separately.

```
<r>
...
<i>0:25.5C,</i>
<j>0:500,1:500,2:200,3:0,</j>
...
</r>
```

3.2 Off-Nominal operations

As described above, the lights will be controlled by the Argus system and not through standard Heliospectra control procedure; therefore much off-nominal operations that are connected to the control of the lights will be referenced by the Argus system. Apart from that, if there is a case that requires the firmware to be upgraded in the lamps the procedure is described below. Other trouble shooting procedures can be found in the User Manual for the LX and RX lights that the lights are based off.

3.2.1 Firmware Upgrade

The firmware of the light is upgraded with the Heliospectra System Assistant. To first download System Assistant follow the instructions below:

1. At our [download page](#) (link) there are Windows and Mac versions of System Assistant. Download the corresponding version for your type of operating system. It is recommended to save the installation file to your desktop for easily accessing the file.

Follow the instructions to perform a firmware upgrade:

1. Download the latest firmware upgrade package from support section at www.heliospectra.com or contact your Heliospectra representative.
2. Start the Heliospectra System Assistant from the control computer on the lamp network.
3. Click Scan to update the lamp list.
4. Select one or several lamps to upgrade from the list.
5. Select System > Update system from the menu.
6. Select the firmware package downloaded in step 1, then click Open.
7. Click Upgrade. A progress bar will show the progress of the firmware upgrade process.
8. Wait until the upgrade process completes. NOTE! Do not turn off the lamp or close the Heliospectra System Assistant during the upgrade process.
9. Click Scan to refresh the lamp list.
10. Verify that the Firmware column shows the new firmware version number for the updated lamps.

3.3 Maintenance and spares

3.3.1 Cleaning

Clean the lights regularly to ensure proper operation:

- If the clear plastic plate covering the LEDs becomes dirty it should be wiped off with a soft damp cloth. A mild detergent can be used if the plate has finger prints or similar smudges. Check monthly.

3.3.2 Spares and spare parts

The project has been equipped with 6 spare units that are to be shipped with the lights hung in the container to Antarctica. It is recommended that upon any light failure that the lights are exchanged as a whole and that they are not to be opened on site for reparations. The lights are very advanced pieces of equipment and any reparations or alterations to the fixtures need to be conducted by a technically trained professional in the field.

3.4 Preparation for shipment

Due to the robust mounting of the fixtures, it has been deemed that no disassembly is required for the shipment to Antarctica.

4 Design lessons learned

4.1 Couplings

The design and BOM was frozen at a very late stage in the project due to numerous changes in the requirements. Therefore, the design was made as such to be able to open the fixture to make changes. This impacted the quality of assuring the nonexistence of water leakage in the fixture. The couplings were then specified to adhere to this possibility and were therefore not qualified to the full extent of the product. Upon installation and integration with the water cooling system, a couple of lights started to leak. This was handled by exchanging the couplings to a version that would not allow for an easy disassembly of the lamps. Because of this change, it is now recommended that the fixtures should only be exchanged if any failure occurs as the lights are no longer able to be disassembled in the same fashion as previously.

Figure 4-1: Picture of old water coupling connection (top left) and new water coupling connection (center).